

Community recommendations for geochemical data, services and analytical capabilities in the 21st century

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11 **Abstract**

The majority of geochemical and cosmochemical research is based upon observations and, in particular, upon the acquisition, processing and interpretation of analytical data from physical samples. The exponential increase in volumes and rates of data acquisition over the last century, combined with advances in instruments, analytical methods and an increasing variety of data types analysed, has necessitated the development of new ways of data curation, access and sharing. Together with novel data processing methods, these changes have enabled new scientific insights and are driving innovation in Earth and Planetary Science research. Yet, as approaches to data-intensive research develop and evolve, new challenges emerge. As large and often global data compilations increasingly form the basis for new research studies, institutional and methodological differences in data reporting are proving to be significant hurdles in synthesising data from multiple sources. Consistent data formats and data acquisition descriptions are becoming crucial to enable quality assessment, reusability and integration of results fostering confidence in available data for reuse. Here, we explore the key challenges faced by the geo- and cosmochemistry community and, by drawing comparisons from other communities, recommend possible approaches to over-

come them. The first challenge is bringing together the numerous sub-disciplines within our community under a common international initiative. One key factor for this convergence will be gaining endorsement from the international geochemical, cosmochemical and analytical societies and associations, journals and institutions. Increased education and outreach, spearheaded by ambassadors recruited from leading scientists across disciplines, will further contribute to raising awareness, and to uniting and mobilising the community. Appropriate incentives, recognition and credit for good data management as well as an improved, user-oriented technical infrastructure will be essential for achieving a cultural change towards an environment in which the effective use and real-time interchange of large datasets is common-place. Finally, the development of best practices for standardised data reporting and exchange, driven by expert committees, will be a crucial step towards making geo- and cosmochemical data more Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable by both humans and machines (FAIR).

12 *Keywords:* FAIR data, data standards, data quality

13 **1. Introduction**

14 Data are the backbone of geochemical and cosmochemical research, and their acquisition
15 and use are central to many aspects of our research and education. Over the last century,
16 an ever-increasing volume of geochemical data have been acquired and used to explore a
17 variety of past, present and future processes in the Earth, environmental and planetary
18 sciences (Fig. 1). The growing rate of data generation is complemented by new capabilities
19 in storing, accessing, processing and modelling of large datasets (e.g. Morrison et al., 2017;
20 Duke et al., 2022; He et al., 2022; Wieser et al., 2022).

21 The increasing need for globally standardised geochemical data has become a com-
22 mon subject of discussion amongst the international scientific community in the last few
23 years (e.g. Stall et al., 2019; Chamberlain et al., 2021; Wyborn et al., 2021; Pourret and
24 Irawan, 2022). Motivated by these developments, the three geochemical data systems

25 EarthChem, GEOROC and AusGeochem held a joint workshop at the Goldschmidt Con-
26 ference 2022: “Earth Science meets Data Science: what are our needs for geochemical data,
27 services and analytical capabilities in the 21st century?” ([https://conf.goldschmidt.](https://conf.goldschmidt.info/goldschmidt/2022/meetingapp.cgi/Session/3301)
28 [info/goldschmidt/2022/meetingapp.cgi/Session/3301](https://conf.goldschmidt.info/goldschmidt/2022/meetingapp.cgi/Session/3301)). This workshop primarily fo-
29 cused on exploring the data and infrastructure requirements for addressing future scientific
30 challenges. More information about the workshop programme, participating data systems
31 and attendees is available in the Supplementary Material. This paper summarises the
32 workshop outcomes and provides recommendations for a global geochemical data frame-
33 work, required to tackle and accomplish the scientific challenges of the 21st century and
34 beyond.

35 **2. Motivation**

36 *2.1. Diversity and Fragmentation of Geochemical Data*

37 We understand geochemistry as the discipline that integrates geology and chemistry
38 by using the principles and tools of chemistry to develop fundamental understanding of
39 the dynamics of geological systems, from the interior of the Earth to its surface envi-
40 ronments on land, in the oceans, and in the air, to planetary systems and the entire
41 galaxy. Geochemistry emerged as a discipline of its own in 1838 and, since then, acquisi-
42 tion and analysis of geochemical data have become pervasive in the Earth, environmental,
43 and planetary sciences (Fairbridge, 1998). Geochemistry is exceedingly diverse with many
44 recognised subdisciplines, including aqueous, organic, inorganic, isotope, bio- and physical
45 geochemistry as well as cosmochemistry. Geochemical data have further applications in
46 other disciplines such as archaeology, environmental science and technology, resource ex-
47 ploration and development (groundwater, minerals, energy), geohealth, oceanography, and
48 agriculture, and are thus relevant to many United Nations Sustainable Development Goals
49 (e.g. Bundschuh et al., 2017; Gill, 2017; Alexakis, 2021; Wyborn and Lehnert, 2021).

50 Geochemical data are incredibly diverse in nature and generally only have two common

Figure 1: Increase in geochemical data published in journals and repositories since the late 19th century. **(a)** Data compiled within the GEOROC database, by publication year of the respective journal articles, as a proxy for the increase in data production within the subdiscipline of igneous geochemistry in the continental realm. Inset: Close-up of earliest publication years. **(b)** Data compiled within the Petrological Database (PetDB) which contains data complementary to GEOROC with a focus on the oceanic realm, mantle xenoliths and tephra. Inset: Close-up of earliest publication years. **(c)** Data compiled within the Astromaterials Data System, including data from the MetBase database, as a proxy for data production within cosmochemistry. **(d)** Cumulative number of data submissions to the EarthChem Library, a domain repository for all subdisciplines of geochemistry. Inset: individual number of data submissions per year.

51 attributes: firstly, they are “Long Tail”, i.e. highly variable and small in volume (Heidorn,
52 2008); and secondly, they are primarily acquired by individual investigators or small teams,
53 often across multiple organisations and disciplines with uncertain funding sustainability.
54 Due to this diversity, many geochemical datasets are stored in incompatible and often
55 inaccessible silos, such as individual computers and locally developed database solutions,
56 or they are restricted to figures without accompanying data tables. As a consequence, and
57 despite numerous data rescue efforts, harnessing the wealth of existing geochemical data
58 is a critical and ongoing challenge.

59 Although there have been many attempts to improve the aggregation, sharing and
60 reuse of geochemical data (e.g. Wyborn and Ryburn, 1989; Carbotte and Lehnert, 2007;
61 Geochemical Society, 2007; Goldstein et al., 2014), present-day practices tend to focus
62 on building geochemical databases in either personal, institutional, national, or program-
63 matic silos with a noticeable divide in approaches to data management among the sectors of
64 academia, government and industry. Most of these databases are built for specific research
65 projects and do not offer a long-term sustainable solution. There are very few standard
66 practices amongst authors and publishers to make data easily shareable and interoperable.
67 As a result, geochemical data are highly fragmented, blocked from discovery and difficult to
68 reuse directly from the source dataset without considerable efforts in reformatting the data.
69 Moreover, the same data are duplicated numerous times into multiple compilations and
70 credit is rarely given to those who funded, collected, and/or analysed the original datasets.
71 This fragmentation has a measurable financial impact: the European Commission esti-
72 mated the annual direct cost of managing non-standardised research data at EUR 10.2bn,
73 with an additional indirect cost to society of EUR 16bn per year (European Commission,
74 2018).

75 *2.2. Drivers and Rationale for Connecting the Silos*

76 A number of important resources for geochemical and cosmochemical data were es-
77 tablished during the past 30 years, including EarthChem (<https://earthchem.org/>),

78 GEOROC (<https://georoc.eu/>), MetBase (<https://metbase.org/>), and the Astroma-
79 terials Data System (<https://www.astromat.org/>). More recent initiatives are National
80 Research Infrastructures in Germany (NFDI4Earth), Europe (EPOS), Australia (AuS-
81 cope), the US (EarthCube), or Norway (NIRD), to name a few. However, barriers around
82 individual data silos remain, hindering simple, inclusive and global access to geochemical
83 data. To overcome these silo walls, we must develop and implement common, community-
84 agreed, global standards for geochemical data and metadata. These standards are critical
85 to making geochemical data Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable to both hu-
86 mans and machines (FAIR; Wilkinson et al., 2016). Not only will FAIR data standards and
87 curation procedures increase the value of new data as they are generated and published,
88 they likewise have large potential for utilising the significant proportion of unpublished
89 geochemical data in research and public sectors from the last century.

90 Recognising that mainstream scientific journals were the most effective agents to rectify
91 problems in data reporting and implement best practices, an Editors Roundtable was held
92 in 2007 as an initiative to bring together editors, publishers, and database providers to
93 implement consistent publication practices for geochemical data. Academic societies such
94 as the Geochemical Society also adopted a policy for geochemical data publication at that
95 time (Geochemical Society, 2007). The Editors Roundtable created and signed a policy
96 statement in January 2009 (version 1.1) that laid out ‘Requirements for the Publication
97 of Geochemical Data’ (Goldstein et al., 2014). Unfortunately, even 14 years on these
98 recommendations are rarely followed.

99 Recently, the nationally-funded, global data systems Astromaterials (USA), Earth-
100 Chem (USA), GEOROC (Germany), EPOS-MSL (European Plate Observing System Mul-
101 tiScale Laboratories, Europe), MetBase (Germany) and AusGeochem (Australia) came
102 together to enable interoperability between their systems. Yet a vast amount of geo-
103 chemical data lies outside these initiatives. In response to Open Science policies and
104 demands from the scientific community, a Town Hall meeting on ‘OneGeochemistry: To-

ward a Global Network of Geochemistry Data’ was held at the AGU Fall Meeting 2019 to raise awareness of the increasingly urgent need for global standards and best practices for geochemical data— aiming towards better sharing and linking of data resources into a global network (<https://www.agu.org/Fall-Meeting-2019/Events/Data-TH23L>). The goal of this meeting was to broaden community awareness of and participation in the initiative and speakers represented relevant stakeholders such as geochemical societies, geochemical journal editors, data infrastructure providers, researchers, and funders. The OneGeochemistry initiative was launched. Since then, the OneGeochemistry initiative regularly leads and contributes to scientific sessions during Goldschmidt, EGU and AGU meetings— including a Great Debate and Webinar at EGU22 (‘Where is my data, where did it come from and how was it obtained? Improving Access to Geoanalytical Research Data’; <https://meetingorganizer.copernicus.org/EGU22/session/42788>; <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=nqjp0ePQU0w>)— as well as international fora such as SciDataCon and the International Science Council’s Committee on Data (CODATA) meetings (e.g. Lehnert et al., 2021; Wyborn et al., 2021).

2.3. *OneGeochemistry Mission*

OneGeochemistry is an international collaboration between multiple national organisations that support geochemistry capability and data production. The focus of this initiative is to better coordinate global efforts in geochemical data standardisation, facilitate communication between groups and lessen duplication of efforts. OneGeochemistry is now taking action, predominantly through volunteer work of its member organisations, to collect, synthesise and promote global, community-driven data conventions and best practices. Such global best practices will enable and simplify the (re)use of geochemical data, making possible a global network of trusted geochemical data, which will accelerate the generation of new geoscientific knowledge and discoveries.

Data standardisation begins with community agreement on concepts and vocabularies used to describe analytical data. Such vocabularies are critical to organise and classify

132 data: they set out the common terminology. We require experts for each data type to
133 come together to develop the required vocabularies in both human and machine readable
134 forms, whilst building on and integrating existing definitions from the broader geoscience
135 terminology and other related domains. The community must then agree to use these
136 vocabularies to refer to their concepts of interest, as well as evolve and govern them as
137 requirements change.

138 In line with modern informatics best practices, all geochemical data will need to comply
139 with the FAIR principles of Wilkinson et al. (2016). OneGeochemistry seeks to make geo-
140 chemical data outputs as well as related inputs (including samples, instruments, software
141 codes):

- 142 1. **Findable (F)** through machine-actionable metadata and the systematic use of unique
143 and persistent identifiers on inputs and outputs;
- 144 2. **Accessible (A)** using standards and internet protocols;
- 145 3. **Interoperable (I)** through common formats that incorporate authoritative and re-
146 ferrable domain vocabularies; and
- 147 4. **Reusable (R)** through use of rich metadata that provide guidelines on provenance,
148 quality and uncertainty, that clearly show identity, funders, and provide open licences.

149 It is also essential to ensure compliance with the CARE and TRUST principles. The
150 CARE Principles for Indigenous Data Governance (Collective Benefit, Authority to Con-
151 trol, Responsibility, and Ethics) protect Indigenous rights and interests in Indigenous data
152 including traditional knowledge, particularly in the sample collection phase (Carroll et al.,
153 2020). The TRUST Principles (Transparency, Responsibility, User focus, Sustainability
154 and Technology) ensure long-term data preservation and trustworthiness in digital reposi-
155 tories. (Lin et al., 2020).

156 Efforts have already been made to set standards for specific analytical data types:
157 Deines et al. (2003); Demetriades et al. (2020, 2022); Boone et al. (2022); Flowers et al.
158 (2022); Brantley et al. (2021); Abbott et al. (2022); Horstwood et al. (2016); Dutton

159 et al. (2017); Walker et al. (2008); Courtney Mustaphi et al. (2019); Schaen et al. (2020);
160 Khider et al. (2019); Damerow et al. (2021); Peng et al. (2022); Wallace et al. (2022).
161 These publications are an excellent first step, however they only cover a subset of the
162 chemical data types and very few conform with the FAIR principles that require data
163 to be machine readable. Hence, these standards need to be converted into the digi-
164 tal space (e.g., the IUPAC Digital Chemistry Initiative; [https://iupac.org/what-we-](https://iupac.org/what-we-do/digital-standards/)
165 [do/digital-standards/](https://iupac.org/what-we-do/digital-standards/)). The next step towards standardisation of geochemical data is
166 to follow Cox et al. (2021) and make the vocabularies, recommended within each stan-
167 dard to define different data types, FAIR and available from online repositories such as
168 Research Vocabularies Australia (RVA, <https://vocabs.ardc.edu.au/>) or FAIRsharing
169 (<https://fairsharing.org/>). Another important point often missing in existing rec-
170 ommendations is a governance structure that allows vocabularies and best practices to
171 evolve.

172 OneGeochemistry aims to become an organisation that coordinates across all geo- and
173 cosmochemical data types, both supporting existing community standards as well as facili-
174 tating the development of new ones where needed. Importantly, OneGeochemistry will act
175 as the facilitator in these efforts: the initiative will neither set standards nor implement
176 them, but rather support the community in doing so. A starting point will be to support
177 the digitisation of existing standards to make them, and the vocabularies defined within
178 them, fully FAIR. Fundamental to OneGeochemistry's approach is ensuring that network-
179 ing common components across disciplines still enables a capacity for deeper disciplinary
180 specialisation. This will be an ongoing, long-term project that must be continually adapted
181 in line with new or improved developments of data acquisition and with support of, and
182 commitment from, the global geochemical and cosmochemical communities.

Figure 2: The sample and data life cycle from acquisition to publication to reuse (adapted from Ramdeen et al., 2022). Tools that support researchers throughout this process include SESAR, a registry for physical samples. AusGeochem, StraboSpot and Sparrow are examples of systems that support researchers from field acquisition of samples through sample preparation and analysis to publication in a domain repository. Repositories such as the EarthChem Library serve the Archiving and Publication of Data, while synthesis databases such as the Astromaterials Data Synthesis, PetDB, GEOROC or MetBase facilitate dissemination and data reuse.

183 **3. Challenges for the Community**

184 This paper tackles challenges faced by both the active research community (predomi-
 185 nantly at academic and government institutions) and the curated data systems that sup-
 186 port this community throughout the research data lifecycle. These data systems can be
 187 grouped into four types: 1) Laboratory Information Management Systems, 2) Repositories,
 188 3) Data Portals, and 4) Synthesis Databases. Firstly, Laboratory Information Management

189 Systems focus on physical samples and cover the first half of the research data lifecycle
190 from sample collection or generation to processing and analysis (Fig. 2). Examples of
191 such systems include AusGeochem (<https://www.auscope.org.au/ausgeochem>), Stra-
192 boSpot (<https://www.strabospot.org/>) and Sparrow (<https://sparrow-data.org/>).
193 Secondly, the final data products derived from samples might then be published in Repos-
194 itories as well as cited in journal publications. Generalist repositories, such as Figshare
195 (<https://figshare.com/>), Dryad (<https://datadryad.org/>) or Zenodo (<https://zenodo.org/>),
196 publish research outputs irrespective of academic discipline and without review. Do-
197 main repositories, in contrast, cater to specific disciplines or subdisciplines and therefore
198 offer data services targeted to the particular requirements of these domains. PANGAEA
199 (<https://www.pangaea.de/>) and GFZ Data Services (<https://bib.telegrafenberg.de/dataservices/>)
200 are examples of domain repositories for the Earth Sciences, whilst the
201 Astromaterials Data Repository (<https://repo.astromat.org/>), the EarthChem Library
202 (<https://earthchem.org/ec1/>) or the GEOROC Data Repository (<https://georoc.eu/>)
203 are domain repositories specifically for geochemical data. Thirdly, Data Portals
204 offer a catalogue of datasets hosted by different repositories. For example, DataONE
205 (<https://dataone.org/>) searches across 44 data repositories of all disciplines operated by
206 research centres, universities, libraries, scientific consortia, non-profit organisations, citizen
207 science initiatives, corporate divisions, governmental and non-governmental organisations.
208 Such data portals greatly increase the discoverability of data products stored in the respec-
209 tive systems by searching through their metadata catalogues, including the title, abstract or
210 keywords of individual datasets. Finally, Synthesis Databases compile individual data pub-
211 lications and harvest data from the scientific literature to enable data discovery and reuse
212 across multiple datasets. In contrast to data portals, synthesis databases do not only sup-
213 port searches across the metadata of datasets in multiple repositories (e.g. title, keywords,
214 etc), they further compile the actual data held in each of these records and allow download
215 of single, combined datasets. Similar to domain repositories, synthesis databases usually

216 specialise in a particular subdiscipline or have a geographical focus. However, in contrast to
217 repositories they do not serve as a data publisher but instead only focus on synthesising and
218 compiling previously published data. Note that we do not consider research datasets de-
219 rived from literature compilations as databases here as they usually are ephemeral, one-off
220 research products that are not continuously curated and more importantly, rarely uniquely
221 identify each analysis so that the author and funder can track citations and measure impact.
222 The Astromaterials Data Synthesis, GEOROC, LEPR (<https://lepr.earthchem.org/>),
223 MetBase and PetDB (<https://search.earthchem.org/>) are all examples of synthesis
224 databases. These databases provide valuable resources not only for further research but
225 also for teaching. Both repositories and synthesis databases also play an important role
226 in data rescue efforts. Figure 3 shows an example of the flow of geochemical data from
227 natural samples through the IEDA2 (Interdisciplinary Earth Data Alliance) and affiliated
228 data systems.

229 In an ideal world, all analytical data produced in a laboratory and subsequently pub-
230 lished in the scientific literature, would eventually be made available in a federated, global
231 data system that makes it easy for others to find, access and reuse these data. Features of
232 such an ideal data system include:

- 233 1. **Relevance & Findability:** A variety of data types are available for all types of
234 sample material (natural and synthetic). It is easy to combine multiple databases
235 to search, capture and organise all existing data. These databases contain mini-
236 mal redundancy and the use of globally unique, persistent and resolvable identifiers
237 (e.g. digital object identifiers, DOIs, and the international generic sample number,
238 IGSN) allows compilation of analyses from the same sample or publication. Database
239 versioning allows reproducibility of previous searches.
- 240 2. **Accessibility:** User access is facilitated by optimised complex queries, for example
241 through a customisable search engine, visualisation, data analysis and export options.
242 Access through standard programming languages guarantees machine-readability.

Figure 3: An example of the flow of geochemical data from natural samples through the IEDA2 (black) and partner (blue) data systems. Together, these data systems cover the entire research data lifecycle as shown in Fig. 2. Note that the EarthChem Portal enables data searches across distinct synthesis databases, in contrast to the data portals described in the text that facilitate metadata searches across different repositories. Not included in this schema is the Library of Experimental Phase Relations (LEPR) for experimental and synthetic materials. For comparison, the AusGeochem system covers stages I to III of this diagram for data produced by Australian geochemistry laboratories.

243 Furthermore, access is free and open to all: there should be no cost to the researcher
 244 in either publishing or accessing data.

245 3. **Data Quality:** Data are reliable and their quality is straightforward to assess, i.e.
 246 they follow a common standard that ensures availability of rich sample and ana-
 247 lytical metadata (e.g. provenance, description of method and analysis conditions).
 248 Completeness of metadata allows assessment of accuracy and precision, and ensures
 249 reproducibility. Both data providers and data users perform QA/QC; any data qual-
 250 ity issues are reported and promptly resolved.

251 4. **Attribution:** Appropriate citation of the people, laboratories, organisations, fun-

252 ders, research artefacts and data is ensured through use of globally unique, persistent
253 and resolvable identifiers and compliance with international metadata standards (e.g.
254 the IGSN for samples, the Open Researcher and Contributor Identifier, ORCID, for
255 authors, the Research Organization Registry, ROR, for institutions; or the DataCite
256 metadata standard).

257 Many of the data systems mentioned above strive to provide such a comprehensive data
258 infrastructure. It is now increasingly recognised that data and metadata capture should
259 start with the collection/production of the sample itself, and not only after data publication
260 (e.g. Damerow et al., 2021). However, there are many challenges along the path towards
261 FAIR geochemical data, many of which have been introduced above. One of the goals of
262 the Goldschmidt 2022 workshop was to investigate these challenges in more detail, so that
263 appropriate solutions for each of them might be developed. These challenges are rooted
264 in the current research culture around geoanalytical data, as well as the limitations of the
265 existing data systems and their often precarious funding situation.

266 *3.1. Challenges for Researchers*

267 The current research culture in geochemistry means that few researchers are willing to
268 share their data (Chamberlain et al., 2021). Although the recent push for open science
269 has benefited the open data landscape, community understanding and adoption are still
270 centred around individuals. The majority of data producers remain reluctant to share their
271 data unless forced by journal or funding requirements: the EarthChem Library reported
272 an increase in data submissions after several of the AGU journals enforced data publica-
273 tions in trusted domain repositories in 2019 (Fig. 1d; https://www.agu.org/Share-and-Advocate/Share/Polycymakers/Position-Statements/Position_Data). Nevertheless,
274 there is still a widespread lack of adoption of these policies by the research community.
275 Common barriers to data sharing include the additional effort of organising and formatting
276 of data, distrust and protection of personal interests, e.g. with additional work in progress,
277 insecurity about copyright and licensing, lack of knowledge about the most appropriate
278

279 repository, lack of time, as well as the costs of sharing data (Stuart et al., 2018; Science
280 et al., 2021; Tedersoo et al., 2021). Yet even those researchers who are willing to share their
281 data are faced with a number of considerable challenges that we discuss in the following.

282 **Lack of consistent guidelines:** Policies on data management vary widely amongst
283 the different funding agencies, institutions, publishers and journals. Funders often require
284 a data management plan at the proposal stage, yet few enforce these requirements once
285 grants are approved. Researchers are neither penalised nor rewarded in response to how
286 they manage their data, prompting the question as to why this requirement exists in the
287 first instance if there is no mechanism for ensuring compliance. In addition, institutional
288 open access policies often do not extend to include research data or a requirement for
289 machine-readable formats— a PDF-copy of published journal articles in the institutional
290 repositories is usually enough to fulfil these guidelines. This effect is compounded by many
291 institutions lacking the resources to support their researchers in appropriate data man-
292 agement. Finally, the publishing landscape is as diverse as the journals available. Each
293 publisher has defined their own policies on data management, and often these guidelines
294 differ for each journal even with the same publisher. The publishers Springer Nature,
295 American Association for the Advancement of Science (AAAS) and American Geophysi-
296 cal Union (AGU) are proponents of consistent data management practices, requiring data
297 publication in domain repositories prior to manuscript acceptance across many of their
298 journals, yet each have developed their own— differing— guidelines on how to comply
299 with this policy. Dedicated data journals, such as Data in Brief (Elsevier) and Scientific
300 Data (Springer Nature), perhaps present a good alternative in requiring data submission to
301 (domain) repositories and, in addition, providing a platform for publishing and describing
302 data that might otherwise never be made public— for example, data from unfinished or
303 abandoned thesis projects or those transcribed from old, non-digital formats. However,
304 most other journals still accept data tables in formats ranging from tabular (CSV or XLS)
305 to text (DOC, PDF) and even image files (JPEG, PNG) as part of supplementary mate-

306 rials or they encourage submission to generalist repositories, such as Figshare, Zenodo or
307 Dryad, where there is no quality control or agreed reporting standards on geochemical data.
308 Researchers, therefore, are faced with the impossible task of navigating these conflicting
309 guidelines, and will generally follow the policy of the journal or publisher they submit to
310 out of fear that their manuscript might otherwise be rejected. When faced with the com-
311 plexity of submission to domain repositories (see below), often the publishing option with
312 the lowest workload is chosen. This behaviour naturally leads to highly heterogeneous data
313 published following very different standards, if any, in very different formats across a wide
314 range of repositories or other data publishers. In addition to the many different formats
315 that prevent data from being easily combined and compared, many datasets remain behind
316 a journal paywall and are very hard to access in the first place. Data availability “upon
317 request” also remains a popular option, even though it has been shown to be burdensome
318 and ineffective as a means for data sharing (Vines et al., 2014; Tedersoo et al., 2021). Even
319 for Science, a journal that adopted an open data policy in 2016, 30% of articles do not
320 publish their data at all, and only for about a quarter of articles can research findings be
321 accurately reproduced (Stodden et al., 2018; Yeston, 2021).

322 **Complexity of data submission:** Good data management takes time. The assem-
323 bling and submission of data tables and related information require time and additional
324 effort outside of the primary process of manuscript submission. Usually, substantial pro-
325 cessing is performed on raw data coming from an analytical instrument. While this process-
326 ing is a common research practice, information on data reduction and reference materials
327 used are often not reported, or only a simplified version is included in the methods or sup-
328 plementary information. Yet, reporting this information is crucial for the reproducibility
329 of data and, therefore, a prerequisite for data submission to domain repositories. This
330 considerable, additional investment of research time and resources is often voluntary, and
331 not appropriately rewarded within the current academic structure (Piwowar et al., 2007;
332 Kim and Stanton, 2012). Even though data publications are increasingly visible via (au-

333 tomatic) indexing in ORCID profiles, for example, they are rarely counted towards the
334 research track record or valued by recruiting and promotion committees. Whilst assigning
335 DOIs to datasets helps to emphasise the value of data publications, the lack of awareness in
336 the broader research community means that these publications are often not appropriately
337 cited. In addition, researchers who consider submitting to domain repositories are often
338 deterred by the additional processing time before the final data publication. The Earth-
339 Chem Library, for example, that specialises in geochemical data, advises a turnaround
340 time ranging from a few days to up to two weeks. PANGAEA, a domain repository for
341 all disciplines within the Earth Sciences, has a data publication timeline of three months.
342 Even though there are good reasons for these timelines— mostly centred around curation
343 as discussed below—, they discourage even more researchers from publishing their data.

344 **Variable quality of the available published data:** A direct result of the lack of
345 guidelines combined with the complexity of data submission is the highly variable quality
346 of the available datasets. The lack of enforced standard formats for publishing geochem-
347 ical data often precludes any quality assessment and, therefore, reuse of published data.
348 Common issues include: dead links or non-existent supplementary material; errors in data
349 reporting; lack of reproducibility due to missing analytical information; and the use of unde-
350 fined abbreviations only understood by the owner of the dataset. Data quality assessment
351 is often impossible due to a lack of analytical details or measures of uncertainties, includ-
352 ing inconsistent units on uncertainty reporting (e.g. standard deviations, standard errors,
353 confidence interval, 1σ vs. 2σ errors, etc.). When compiling data from multiple sources,
354 additional challenges include inconsistent, non-standardised terminology (e.g. eclogite vs
355 arclogite) and missing units of measurement. Finally, the original owner, funder, and/or
356 creator of the data are rarely credited in compiled datasets.

357 **Complexity of citation for data compilation work:** The inclusion of all refer-
358 ences to the original data sources in published data tables, which is common standard for
359 data collections, does not automatically provide credit in measurable form. In order for

360 these citations to be tracked, references must be included in the ‘References’ sections of
361 scholarly literature. Unfortunately, journals commonly limit the total number of citations
362 allowed (often between 40–70) and ask authors to move any additional references into the
363 supplemental information. Yet, references in supplemental information are not properly
364 indexed, not linked to the manuscript, nor tracked accurately— all of which is essential to
365 enable reproducible research and for researchers and institutions to trace data usage and
366 receive appropriate credit for their work. The new “Complex Citations Working Group”
367 of the Research Data Alliance (RDA; [https://www.rd-alliance.org/groups/complex-](https://www.rd-alliance.org/groups/complex-citations-working-group)
368 [citations-working-group](https://www.rd-alliance.org/groups/complex-citations-working-group)) is currently developing a method for handling the citation
369 of large numbers of objects— particularly datasets, software, and physical samples— in
370 scholarly work (Agarwal et al., 2021). They propose the term ‘reliquary’ to describe a col-
371 lection/package of aggregated individual datasets that make up a data compilation used
372 within a specific article. By citing this ‘data reliquary’, all component datasets would
373 also receive a citation without needing to be included in the article reference list. Work
374 by the RDA group now focuses on (1) the development of a scalable solution and the
375 infrastructure to enable credit for each individual element of this ‘reliquary’, and (2) its
376 acknowledgement and implementation by journals.

377 **Sensitive data:** Finally, an important consideration within both the FAIR and CARE
378 principles is how to handle sensitive data that should only be discoverable by certain, autho-
379 rised persons or only available after an embargo period. This access control is particularly
380 important for geochemical data produced or funded by industry and for agencies that deal
381 with classified information. Fortunately, good technical solutions already exist, simply re-
382 quiring clear licensing of datasets and the ability of repositories to handle management of
383 temporary embargo periods during the publication phase. Such solutions are already im-
384 plemented in many geochemical repositories, including, for example, CUAHSI HydroShare
385 (<https://www.hydroshare.org/>) or the EarthChem Library.

386 3.2. *Challenges for Data Systems*

387 Some of the challenges for researchers detailed above are related to current limitations
388 of data repositories and synthesis databases. One major issue lies with the resources avail-
389 able to these data systems and the sustainability of funding. Long-term staffing solutions
390 for data curators that assist researchers with data submissions are vital for data systems.
391 The advantage of publishing data in domain repositories is that the research data are doc-
392 umented in a format specific to the discipline and the respective data type, which ensures
393 that data quality can be easily assessed and data users have greater trust in individual
394 datasets. By collecting data in domain repositories, they are also more visible and easier
395 to discover for others in the field. Even though data sharing practices vary widely between
396 scientific disciplines, the greater discoverability of datasets published in curated domain
397 repositories often leads to greater reuse— and ultimately citation— of these data and the
398 associated publications (e.g. Piwowar et al., 2007; Science et al., 2021). Yet in order to
399 consistently provide this service, domain repositories need to employ curators with domain
400 expertise who carefully review each data submission. Many researchers of today are not
401 familiar with all intricacies of data management, and hence data submissions are often not
402 consistent. While it takes the researchers a considerable amount of time to collate this
403 information, repository curators then need to invest further time to convert submissions
404 to their internal standard and ensure all data and metadata are transparent and easy to
405 understand by third parties.

406 More often than not, repositories are not funded for this additional work and are strug-
407 gling with staffing issues. These problems arise because many of the data systems catering
408 to a specific domain were born out of research projects that succeeded in attracting ad-
409 ditional funding to further develop their infrastructure. However, this funding is usually
410 temporary and restricted to the development of new technologies or services— system main-
411 tenance and curation are rarely funded by national science foundations. What is more,
412 these data systems compete for funding with researchers within their domain. Although

413 it has long been recognised that the benefits of open data infrastructure, and the measur-
414 able resources saved by their existence, far outweigh the costs of building and maintaining
415 this infrastructure (e.g. Ball et al., 2004), most data systems still struggle for long-term
416 survival. Far too often, data systems that are widely used by the research community are
417 orphaned because of discontinued funding: MetPetDB and SedDB are pertinent examples
418 of such systems that are no longer maintained, and at worst are no longer available to the
419 community.

420 The availability of resources is intricately linked with community-uptake of domain
421 repository services. For many data systems, it is an ongoing struggle to entice more
422 researchers to submit their data, something which they require as an indicator for their
423 success and continued funding. With additional resources, data systems could better raise
424 awareness within the community, as well as expand their user support, in turn increasing
425 the number of datasets submitted by researchers. Ideally, resources would also be allocated
426 to provide training materials and build guided workflows that operate across repositories
427 and other publication platforms to make it easy for researchers to follow best practices.

428 **4. Approaches to similar challenges in other communities**

429 Despite the various challenges outlined in the previous section, this topic is not new
430 and other disciplines have successfully begun adopting FAIR data practices. In analytical
431 science, particularly where the same data type is collected by multiple laboratories and
432 institutions, informed decisions on whether or how to (re)use any digital analytical dataset
433 is dependent on a consideration of what practices have been used to obtain the data and the
434 provision of information about the quality specifications (Peng et al., 2022). The following
435 summarises successful approaches to data standardisation and quality assurance in other
436 communities that the geochemistry community can learn from.

437 4.1. Chemistry

438 The International Union of Pure and Applied Chemistry (IUPAC) has a record of over
439 100 years in fostering a global consensus to define and develop a common and systematic
440 nomenclature for chemistry. IUPAC has developed the International Chemical Identifier
441 (InChI; Heller et al., 2013), a non-proprietary identifier for chemical substances that
442 provides a standard way to encode molecular information. IUPAC has also produced a
443 series of colour books that are regarded as the world’s authoritative resource for chemical
444 nomenclature, terminology, and symbols. International committees of experts in the
445 relevant sub-disciplines of chemistry draft the recommendations that are then ratified by
446 IUPAC’s Interdivisional Committee on Terminology, Nomenclature and Symbols (ICTNS;
447 <https://iupac.org/body/027/>). The Terminology definitions are published by IUPAC
448 and include books for

449 1. Naming Chemical Structures

- 450 • Blue Book: Nomenclature of Organic Chemistry
- 451 • Red Book: Nomenclature of Inorganic Chemistry
- 452 • White Book: Biochemical Nomenclature

453 2. Describing Chemistry Concepts:

- 454 • Orange Book: Terminology for Analytical Methods
- 455 • Purple Book: Polymer Terminology and Nomenclature
- 456 • Silver Book: Properties in Clinical Laboratory Sciences
- 457 • Green Book: Quantities, Units and Symbols in Physical Chemistry

458 Other IUPAC initiatives include the Gold Book Compendium of Chemical Terminology
459 (<https://goldbook.iupac.org/>), the Commission on Isotopic Abundances and Atomic
460 Weights (<https://www.ciaaw.org/>) and the Machine Actionable Periodic Table (<https://pubchem.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/ptable/>). Advancement of digital activities and strategy
461

462 within IUPAC largely sits with the Committee on Publications and Cheminformatics Data
463 Standards. IUPAC is currently transforming from a Centre of Excellence for Chemistry
464 Standards to a Centre of Excellence for Digital Chemistry Standards. Many of their digital
465 standards could be leveraged by the global geochemistry community (Stall et al., 2020).

466 IUPAC is primarily a volunteer-based organisation with a modest amount of project
467 funding primarily supported through subventions paid by its member bodies (chemical so-
468 cieties or national academies, and some publications income). A small staff office supports
469 the organisation generally, but most volunteers utilise basic infrastructure of their organi-
470 sations while they work on projects. After the life of the projects, standard specifications
471 are generally available as open access publications. Further development and ongoing
472 support are primarily coordinated through partnerships with external and affiliated or-
473 ganisations. For example, the InChI Trust is a member-supported charity organisation
474 affiliated with IUPAC who develops and maintains the code-base that encapsulates the
475 IUPAC InChI standard specification. Organisations contributing to the InChI Trust in-
476 clude journal publishers, chemical societies, government organisations, software vendors
477 and academic organisations.

478 4.2. Crystallography

479 Crystallography has a long history of discipline standardisation starting with develop-
480 ment of the Crystallographic Information Framework (CIF) in 1991 under the auspices of
481 the International Union of Crystallography (IUCr). The CIF standard is a general, flexible
482 and easily extensible free-format archive file that was designed to be a machine-readable
483 standard for submissions to *Acta Crystallographica* and to crystallographic databases (Hall
484 et al., 1991). A CIF dictionary also stores the name, version and time of update, thus
485 enabling precise citation of the standards used to support a particular data set (Hall and
486 Cook, 1995; Hall and McMahon, 2016). Domain repositories ensure the long term preserva-
487 tion and access to derived results and processed data published in standard formats (Bruno
488 et al., 2017; Groom et al., 2016; Bergerhoff and Brown, 1987; Berman et al., 2003). These

489 crystallographic repositories also support joint workflows with journal publishers that lower
490 technical barriers to data publication by researchers. Further, domain repositories provide
491 services that enable the discovery and reuse of both data and derived knowledge across
492 domains in academia and industry (Taylor and Wood, 2019). For example, the IUCr is
493 taking a lead in ensuring that the preservation of raw diffraction data is viable at a number
494 of distributed and centralised data archives, each of which registers a dataset and uniquely
495 identifies it with a persistent identifier (Kroon-Batenburg et al., 2022). The IUCr provides
496 tools with online validation checks and validation of the data is part of the peer review
497 process for journals (Spek, 2020). Some journals that publish papers on crystallography
498 also sponsor the development of validation tools.

499 Data infrastructure in crystallography is funded through a variety of mechanisms in-
500 cluding research grants, subscription and licensing, and governmental support (Bruno et al.,
501 2017). The development of standards in crystallography is supported by IUCr, with the
502 checkCIF service being supported by sponsorship from publishing organisations. Standard
503 activities also rely heavily on volunteer effort as the scientific unions are limited in the
504 level of support and coordination they can provide. The work of the Worldwide Protein
505 Data Bank (wwPDB) in structural biology is primarily supported by direct funding from
506 government. Conversely, data organisations supporting chemical crystallography do not
507 receive direct public funding and must generate their own revenue, which is typically done
508 by charging industry and academia for access to value-added software and services.

509 *4.3. Seismology*

510 Another example in the development of global community standards for a geoscience
511 data type has been the International Federation of Digital Seismograph Networks (FDSN;
512 <https://www.fdsn.org/>) which is a commission of the International Association for Seis-
513 mology and Physics of the Earth’s Interior (IASPEI) of the International Union of Geodesy
514 and Geophysics (IUGG). The FDSN began in 1984 when multiple countries agreed to create
515 a global network around those scientists using broadband instrumentation compatible with

516 community developed specifications (Dziewonski, 1994). In 1987 expert groups within the
517 FDSN were instrumental in the development of a universal standard for the distribution
518 of broadband waveform data and related parametric information, the SEED format (Stan-
519 dard for Exchange of Earthquake Data). The SEED format was adopted by instrument
520 manufacturers and has since gone through several evolutions. The FDSN also developed a
521 specification that defines RESTful web service interfaces for accessing common FDSN data
522 types online and publishes a list of Federated Data Centres that provide FDSN-compliant
523 web services (<https://www.fdsn.org/webservices/datacenters/>). Network operators
524 can apply for FDSN Network codes through the FDSN website to provide unique identifiers
525 for seismological data streams, which are required in publications to uniquely identify and
526 attribute the networks that generated the data (Evans et al., 2015). FDSN is an inter-
527 national non-governmental organisation with volunteer membership (Suárez et al., 2008).
528 All funding is derived from voluntary contributions by member institutions.

529 *4.4. Geological Map Data*

530 In 2003, the GeoSciML (Geoscience Markup Language) project was initiated under the
531 auspices of the Commission for Geoscience Information (CGI) working group on Data
532 Model Collaboration and endorsed by the International Union of Geological Sciences.
533 GeoSciML is an XML-based data transfer standard for the exchange of digital geoscien-
534 tific information, which is mainly focussed on the representation and description of features
535 found on geological maps, but is extensible to other geoscience data such as drilling, sam-
536 pling and analytical data (Sen and Duffy, 2005). In 2007, GeoSciML was adopted by the
537 OneGeology initiative to underpin and improve the accessibility of global, regional and
538 national geological map data (Jackson and Wyborn, 2008).

539 *4.5. The Oceans Best Practice System and IODP*

540 The Ocean Best Practices System (OBPS, www.oceanbestpractices.org), is an ini-
541 tiative of the global Intergovernmental Oceanographic Commission (IOC) of UNESCO,

542 supported by the International Oceanographic Data and Information Exchange (IODE)
543 and the Global Oceans Observing System (GOOS). The OBPS site supports technolog-
544 ical solutions and community approaches to ensure FAIR methods and associated data
545 and to facilitate the development, documentation and sharing of ocean best practices. As
546 of 1 March 2023, the OBPS site contains 1787 best practice documents from 52 institu-
547 tions/organisations: as new documents are submitted, they are reviewed and endorsed by
548 expert teams (Przeslawski et al., 2022). OBPS further runs an ambassador programme
549 to promote equitable access to ocean best practices across communities, disciplines, and
550 regions.

551 Each institution/organisation can submit their best practice documents including qual-
552 ity documents specific to their data acquisition programmes. The Australian Integrated
553 Marine Observing System (IMOS), for example, operates a wide range of observing equip-
554 ment throughout Australia’s coastal and open oceans and makes all of its data openly and
555 freely accessible. Documents related to the quality of their datasets, including quality speci-
556 fications, quality evaluation, execution and dissemination are published by IMOS on the in-
557 ternational OBPS site (Ruth and Atkins, 2022, <https://repository.oceanbestpractices.org/handle/11329/556>). Publication of best practice documents in a single site from so
559 many organisations leads to convergence and ultimately globalisation of best practices,
560 meaning that a practice can be accessible and usable in multiple regions. At the same
561 time, best practices can be adapted to match regional infrastructure capabilities (Przes-
562 lawski et al., 2022).

563 The International Oceans Discovery Program (IODP, the successor of the Ocean Drilling
564 Program, ODP; <https://www.iodp.org/>) further requires that samples collected on their
565 cruises are archived in one of three recommended repositories. Access to samples is open
566 and transparent to scientists, educators, museums and outreach officers, but regulated by
567 strict policies that ensure their appropriate use and specify the reporting of any research
568 outcomes derived from these samples (<https://www.iodp.org/top-resources/program->

569 documents/policies-and-guidelines/519-iodp-sample-data-and-obligations-policy-
570 implementation-guidelines-may-2018-for-expeditions-starting-october-2018-and-
571 later/file). These outcomes are made available through the integrated data and publi-
572 cation portal SEDIS (Scientific Earth Drilling Information System; [http://sedis.iodp.](http://sedis.iodp.org/)
573 [org/](http://sedis.iodp.org/)).

574 Core funding for OBPS is provided jointly by co-sponsors IODE and GOOS (both in
575 turn funded through the International Oceanographic Commission, IOC). Any technologi-
576 cal developments and implementation of the OBPS objectives and community recommen-
577 dations has to be supplemented by external project funding, such as IMOS. The work of
578 OBPS is overseen by a UNESCO-funded project manager and 24 volunteer steering group
579 members.

580 *4.6. What can be learned from these initiatives?*

581 The examples from crystallography, chemistry, seismology, geology and oceanography
582 demonstrate that it is indeed possible to unite community efforts and together define,
583 implement and enforce best practices and standards for data reporting at an international
584 level. The geochemical and cosmochemical communities can benefit by implementing many
585 common threads outlined in the above initiatives, including:

- 586 1. Securing endorsements from recognised, authoritative groups that are connected to
587 leading International Science Unions/organisations; in some cases, these groups also
588 provide limited funding;
- 589 2. Establishing expert committees for developing data standards and regularly updating
590 these standards as additional requirements emerge;
- 591 3. Publishing community-agreed, time-stamped standards and vocabularies online in
592 both human and machine-readable formats in governed, sustainable repositories;
- 593 4. Connecting with funding agencies to adopt commonly defined standards and enforce
594 research data management plans and data submissions;

- 595 5. Connecting with publishers and editors to enforce compliance with data standards
596 within publications;
- 597 6. Developing and implementing tools that validate data standards compliance;
- 598 7. Enforcing data submission to domain repositories that work with publishers to im-
599 plement standards and ensure long-term preservation and increased discoverability
600 of data;
- 601 8. Adoption of standard data and file formats by instrument manufacturers;
- 602 9. Developing education and outreach programs to teach data management and dissem-
603 inate existing standards and best practices for data users and contributors.

604 **5. The Path Forward: OneGeochemistry**

605 During the workshop at Goldschmidt 2022, organisers and participants discussed pos-
606 sible solutions to the aforementioned challenges and towards the goal of a standardised
607 network of geochemical data resources. The options promising the highest short-term im-
608 pact are: official endorsement of the OneGeochemistry initiative; establishment of expert
609 committees to collect and define best practices for each data type; and a broad education
610 and outreach programme that highlights the benefits of community engagement in this
611 issue. Each of these strategies is discussed in detail below.

612 *5.1. Endorsement*

613 Standards and data management should be developed bottom-up but need to be en-
614 forced top-down. As a consequence, OneGeochemistry is pursuing endorsement from (i)
615 societies, (ii) publishers, (iii) funders and (iv) instrument manufacturers to gain authority
616 for the initiative and thus increase community participation.

617 *5.1.1. Societies and Unions*

618 The heterogeneity of geochemical data and the multiple purposes that geochemistry can
619 be used for, has resulted in geochemistry being a part of at least four International Sci-
620 ence Council (ISC) Science Unions and tens, if not hundreds, of geochemical associations,

621 societies, and commissions at both international and national level. The four main unions
622 that are relevant to geochemical and cosmochemical data include the International Union
623 of Geological Sciences (IUGS), International Union of Geodesy and Geophysics (IUGG),
624 International Union of Crystallography (IUCr) and the International Union of Pure and
625 Applied Chemistry (IUPAC).

626 As of December 2022, the OneGeochemistry initiative is acting as the OneGeochem-
627 istry CODATA Working Group under the International Science Council to bring together
628 all the disparate initiatives that are happening in geochemistry across Scientific Unions,
629 Associations, Societies and Commissions ([https://codata.org/initiatives/decadal-](https://codata.org/initiatives/decadal-programme2/worldfair/onegeochemistry-wg/)
630 [programme2/worldfair/onegeochemistry-wg/](https://codata.org/initiatives/decadal-programme2/worldfair/onegeochemistry-wg/)). Over the next two years, this Working
631 Group will be utilised to recruit a larger membership base to the initiative that will then
632 be able to vote on a long-term governance structure for OneGeochemistry. The OneGeo-
633 chemistry interim board has so far secured endorsement from the following six international
634 geochemical societies and associations: the Geochemical Society, the European Association
635 of Geochemistry, the Association of Applied Geochemists, the International Association of
636 Geochemistry, the Meteoritical Society and the IUGS commission on Global Geochemical
637 Baselines. A final decision is pending from the International Association of Geoanalysts
638 and the International Association of Geochemists. These developments lend authority to
639 OneGeochemistry as the trusted international initiative tasked with bringing together the
640 community and coordinate global efforts in geochemical data standardisation. Society en-
641 dorsement will further help disseminate the goals and activities of OneGeochemistry to a
642 broad membership throughout the geochemical sub-disciplines, and increase participation
643 in the initiative. Additional national and/or sub-disciplinary societies will be contacted in
644 the future and the OneGeochemistry board invites suggestions and recommendations from
645 the community.

646 5.1.2. *Publishers*

647 OneGeochemistry will continue the discussion with journal publishers and editors to
648 raise awareness for the need for data standards in geochemistry to be enforced. The
649 Commitment Statement developed by the Coalition for Publishing Data in the Earth
650 and Space Sciences (COPDESS; [https://copdess.org/enabling-fair-data-project/
651 commitment-statement-in-the-earth-space-and-environmental-sciences/](https://copdess.org/enabling-fair-data-project/commitment-statement-in-the-earth-space-and-environmental-sciences/)) has united
652 many of the repositories, publishers, societies, institutions and infrastructure in an agree-
653 ment to uphold minimum standards. OneGeochemistry will build upon this commitment
654 and, through town halls and other meetings at international conferences, will work towards
655 establishing domain repositories as trusted data publishers that collaborate with journals
656 and publishers to ensure that data submitted to a journal comply with agreed community
657 standards and the FAIR principles.

658 5.1.3. *Funders*

659 As a community we need to communicate with the national and regional funding agen-
660 cies to alert them to our requirements for data management. Many funders have FAIR data
661 policies but most do not yet enforce them or check compliance. In addition, funders play an
662 important role in guiding the academic credit system. For example, the German Research
663 Foundation (DFG) recently changed their rules to recognise article preprints, data sets
664 or software packages as research outcomes, which is an important and positive signal to
665 the scientific community ([https://www.dfg.de/en/research_funding/announcements_
666 proposals/2022/info_wissenschaft_22_61/index.html](https://www.dfg.de/en/research_funding/announcements_proposals/2022/info_wissenschaft_22_61/index.html)).

667 5.1.4. *Instrument Manufacturers*

668 At Goldschmidt 2022, members of the OneGeochemistry interim board connected with
669 some of the geochemical instrument manufacturers, who were very supportive of the ini-
670 tiative and committed to implementing community-agreed data, metadata and formatting
671 standards once they were developed and accepted. As shown by the example from the seis-

672 mological community, support and adoption by instrument manufacturers of community-
673 agreed data standards, aided by common file formats, is crucial to their widespread imple-
674 mentation within laboratories. The increasing adoption of electronic laboratory notebooks,
675 for example, could be exploited to implement data standards and provide a direct data
676 pipeline into certified domain repositories.

677 *5.2. Expert Committees*

678 Multiple best practices and recommendations for specific data types, analytical tech-
679 niques or sub-disciplines have already been defined and are variably adhered to across
680 the globe. A growing number of publications aim to establish agreement on minimum
681 variables and vocabularies for various geochemical data types Deines et al. (2003); Deme-
682 triades et al. (2020, 2022); Boone et al. (2022); Flowers et al. (2022); Brantley et al. (2021);
683 Abbott et al. (2022); Horstwood et al. (2016); Dutton et al. (2017); Walker et al. (2008);
684 Courtney Mustaphi et al. (2019); Schaen et al. (2020); Khider et al. (2019); Damerow et al.
685 (2021). Effective development of scientific standards requires a participatory framework
686 with a need for ongoing, open dialogue within and across research communities (Yarmey
687 and Baker, 2013). The larger the size of the community that agrees and commits to a
688 particular standard, the larger the community that can share and reuse data, particularly
689 in machine-to-machine environments. Hence, to enable global data exchange, we need to
690 harmonise and curate these existing standards through a number of expert committees
691 that are endorsed and/or recognised by authoritative, international geochemical societies
692 and unions. The task of these expert committees would be to compile and further develop
693 standards for each distinct analytical technique or related groups of analytical methods. A
694 committee would be made up of experts within a specific method that are representative
695 of the diversity of users for each data type, including geographical regions, institutions and
696 career levels.

697 OneGeochemistry’s role will be to facilitate and support these expert committees, as
698 well as to disseminate best practice recommendations and invite feedback from the wider

699 community. In addition, OneGeochemistry will set up a technical committee that converts
700 existing standards into machine-readable format. Overall, the focus of the OneGeochem-
701 istry initiative is to coordinate global efforts in geochemical data standardisation, facilitate
702 communication amongst distributed groups and thus minimise duplication and redundancy.
703 In a first step, OneGeochemistry will work with the wider community to compile exist-
704 ing standards, determine which additional data types require standards/vocabularies and
705 which analytical methods are currently in use or have been used in the past for each data
706 type. The role of the expert committees would then be to:

- 707 1. Compile lists of existing standards or best practices (including data models and vo-
708 cabularies) and ensure they are in the public domain, accessible online in a repository
709 or vocabulary service, such as OBPS and RVA, respectively;
- 710 2. Review neighbouring fields and disciplines that have already defined data standards
711 to ensure interoperability (e.g. IUPAC terminologies, government agencies or indus-
712 try standards);
- 713 3. Provide governance to existing standards and harmonise where possible;
- 714 4. Monitor and update each agreed upon standard as needed;
- 715 5. Develop new data standards where required.

716 The technical committee led by OneGeochemistry would then work with the expert com-
717 mittees to digitise these standards and make them FAIR. A timeframe of two years per
718 thematic expert committee is envisaged, culminating in a formal publication of the recom-
719 mended standard and its presentation to the community at one of the annual workshops
720 facilitated by OneGeochemistry.

721 All community-agreed standards are to be published through the ‘Brown Book’, part of
722 the IUPAC Colour Books Series described in Section 4 above which has been offered to One-
723 Geochemistry. With this Brown Book the geochemistry community will be able to publish
724 any nomenclature, terminology or standards that are not already covered in the geochem-
725 istry literature. This resource will be invaluable not only in documenting nomenclatures

726 defined by the geochemical expert committees, but also in ensuring that relevant, existing
727 digital chemical standards are leveraged wherever possible (e.g., the Machine-Accessible
728 Periodic Table).

729 A successful example of an existing expert committee in geochemistry is the Tephra
730 Community that has developed data submission templates for the EarthChem Library
731 (Wallace et al., 2022). EarthChem has further recently started a working group to develop
732 a method directory. Whilst we acknowledge the risk that this modular approach might
733 further divide the community, we propose that it is the most viable solution to: 1) In-
734 volve the community in the process of developing data standards; 2) Provide well-defined,
735 feasible work packages with clear credit/reward/outcome that will motivate community-
736 participation; and 3) Give authority to the standards developed to ensure they are ac-
737 cepted by the wider community. To contribute to or join the OneGeochemistry initia-
738 tive please visit www.onegeochemistry.org for more information and contact onegeochem-
739 istry@codata.org.

740 *5.3. Incentives, Education & Outreach*

741 We recognise that a critical component for the success of OneGeochemistry is increasing
742 outreach and dissemination while establishing appropriate incentives that invite more com-
743 munity members to join. An unexpected outcome of the Goldschmidt 2022 workshop was
744 the observation how poorly known the existing data systems are, especially among early
745 career researchers. Through the OneGeochemistry initiative we hope to achieve greater
746 community engagement via (i) passive advertising of data efforts within research presenta-
747 tions and publications; (ii) virtual campaigns and the open sharing of resources; and (iii)
748 active training through workshops and data mentoring programmes. Whilst this active
749 training can be primarily facilitated by members of the OneGeochemistry board, passive
750 advertising and sharing of resources rely on community participation. For example, passive
751 advertising may include the proper attribution of data systems in publications, following
752 citation guidelines and templates provided by the systems, or the addition of data sys-

753 tem logos to presentation materials (e.g. conference slides, posters, graphical abstracts).
754 Virtual campaigns include a broad social media presence (e.g. on Twitter, LinkedIn),
755 blog posts, webinars and a dedicated YouTube channel to disseminate tutorials and teach
756 data management skills. All of these activities would greatly benefit from the participa-
757 tion of a broad group of active community members and ‘*OneGeochemistry ambassadors*’
758 could drive these initiatives. Ambassadors are envisaged as early to mid-career, cutting-
759 edge researchers that promote good data management following current best practices and
760 standards. Assisted by the OneGeochemistry board members, ambassadors will spread
761 awareness in the communities of the importance of data management in geo- and cosmo-
762 chemistry, the existing landscape of data systems, and inspire new and future generations
763 to contribute. In parallel, OneGeochemistry and its participating data systems would con-
764 tinue to host workshops at scientific conferences, organise data hackathons, contribute to
765 the Data Help Desks coordinated by ESIP at major Earth Science conferences such as the
766 AGU Fall Meeting, the EGU General Assembly and the Geological Society of America
767 meeting (<https://www.esipfed.org/data-help-desk>) and hold Data FAIR workshops
768 (<https://data.agu.org/datafair/>). In addition, data management could be integrated
769 into mentoring schemes at these conferences and inter-institution and international data
770 mentoring programs could focus on available resources in the communities.

771 While communicating and advertising OneGeochemistry, we must always be aware of
772 motivations and incentives (or disincentives) to contribute to standard development, data
773 publication and global databases for each stakeholder. Options to increase community
774 uptake of data sharing practices have been discussed at length in other communities and
775 center around a balance between the perceived cost *versus* benefit of data sharing (e.g.
776 Kim and Stanton, 2012; Kidwell et al., 2016). Yet, the precise incentives will differ widely
777 between different groups in the community (Fig. 4). For OneGeochemistry, the focus is
778 on engaging:

- 779 • **Publishers and editors** who ensure peer review, storage and release of datasets in

780 certified domain repositories prior to publication.

781 • **Funding agencies** who require compliance with certified standards, and provide
782 necessary funds for data curation and staff.

783 • **Data repositories** who are key to storing, curating and making geoanalytical data
784 FAIR.

785 • **Government surveys/agencies** who have a long history of generating and archiv-
786 ing publicly funded research data as well as industry data.

787 • **Professional societies/science unions/associations** who can both endorse and
788 help to promote the standards/best practices.

789 • **Instrument manufacturers** who can ensure any data generated with their instru-
790 ments and output by their software are compliant with standards.

791 • **Laboratory managers** and other geoanalytical data producers to ensure consis-
792 tency and quality of geochemical data at the point of generation.

793 • **Researchers** who generate, (re)use and publish geochemical data.

794 For *researchers*, the main incentive for engaging in good data management practices is
795 credit received towards their scientific track record. As more funding, recruitment and pro-
796 motion bodies start considering more than journal publications as a measurable research
797 output, data publications in domain repositories will gain importance. OneGeochemistry
798 and/or its member data systems will further strive to support researchers through ac-
799 knowledging the number and quality of individual contributions on their websites or, as
800 is common practice with software, through regular version releases. Tracking of citations
801 to data publications independently of a related research paper will provide an additional
802 measure of impact of specific research outputs. Tracking data citations is also a conve-
803 nient way for *funders, institutions* and *laboratories* to measure their impact. Both ‘data

Figure 4: The place of OneGeochemistry within the broader research data landscape (adapted from OECD, 2017). Each group of stakeholders has different needs and motives for contributing to or enforcing FAIR data practices. Blue circles symbolise the role of OneGeochemistry in coordinating expert committees and facilitating education and ambassadorship.

804 reliquaries’ and the new ‘smart citation’ frameworks, such as scite_, are promising develop-
 805 ments that will aid this cause. For *instrument manufacturers*, clear guidance for data and
 806 file formats through community-agreed standards would significantly reduce the resources
 807 spent on developing custom data formats for each analytical instrument. At the same
 808 time, proprietary file formats need not be forfeited as long as final data outputs follow the
 809 community-agreed standards.

810 Industry, such as mining or environmental companies, have been omitted from the

811 list since this initiative is born out of the academic (and governmental research) domain.
812 However, we acknowledge that these companies produce large data volumes and we would
813 welcome future contact and participation with industry representatives. Some countries,
814 such as Australia, already require that all industry data be made available to local geolog-
815 ical surveys after a certain time period— providing an incentive for companies to comply
816 with common data standards to facilitate data sharing, whilst still ensuring a competitive
817 advantage through time-limited, confidential agreements.

818 **6. Conclusions**

819 There is an urgent need in the geochemistry and cosmochemistry communities to define
820 data-type specific best practices and standards for reporting geoanalytical data. Only
821 once these best practices exist, are implemented in research workflows and are consistently
822 followed will geoanalytical data become easy to find, trust and reuse for education or further
823 data-driven research that is increasingly employed to tackle the next big, data intensive
824 and complex scientific questions. We propose that the international OneGeochemistry
825 initiative enacts this change, driven and supported by the community, through facilitating
826 a global, online network of machine-readable data that is persistent, interoperable and
827 reusable, and above all minimises duplication. Once the community has adopted and
828 fully integrated a culture of standardised data and metadata reporting practices, such a
829 framework will also ensure reliable attribution of those who collected, analysed, curated
830 and made accessible any geochemical and cosmochemical data. Endorsement by societies,
831 publishers and funders will give the OneGeochemistry initiative authority to establish
832 expert committees that develop and promote best practices and standards for specific
833 data types. Community engagement and participation at all stages of the process will be
834 pursued through active outreach and dissemination.

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867 **Appendix A. Supplementary Material**

868 The Supplementary Material contains additional information on the Goldschmidt 2022
869 workshop “Earth Science meets Data Science: what are our needs for geochemical data, ser-
870 vices and analytical capabilities in the 21st century?”, including the workshop programme,
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